

Symmetries in New Situations and Their Realisation in Some Systems

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Li's higher order symmetries have been examined in some new situations for transport processes where the total rate processes are obtained by the linear combinations of processes involving unequal order of independence and uneven number of fluxes. Attempt has also been made to examine a few cases of practical interest wherein these symmetries appear to be physically meaningful.

L'S general symmetry relations^{1,2} which follow as a mathematical consequence³⁻⁵ for a general class of linear transformations involving any number of fluxes, so well known in thermodynamics of irreversible processes⁶⁻⁸, have been discussed by a number of investigators^{6,9-11}. Subsequent analysis of the subject in a little more detail has revealed that in addition to the general symmetries envisaged earlier⁹⁻¹¹ there exist some other kind of symmetries also^{10,12}. We have named them as special symmetries and the conditions under which these may be realised have also been elaborated¹². It may be pointed out that some special types of linear combination of the fluxes in question are the prerequisite for the realisation of such special symmetries. We proceed to discuss in the present communication a few implications which arise when the total rate processes are formed by the linear combination of (i) unlike order of independence and (ii) unequal number of fluxes.

Furthermore we also try to point out a few appropriate situations where higher order symmetries are visualised in correct perspectives.

Discussion

It has been shown earlier¹¹ that if the original rate processes J_i ($i=1, 2, \dots, r$) with conjugate forces X_i be represented as

$$J_i = \left(\frac{\partial J_i}{\partial X_i} \right)_0 X_i + \frac{1}{2!} \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_i}{\partial X_i^2} \right)_0 X_i^2 + \dots \quad \dots(1)$$

and the total rate processes J'_i as

$$\begin{pmatrix} J'_1 \\ J'_2 \\ \vdots \\ J'_r \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} n_{11} & n_{12} & \dots & n_{1r} \\ n_{21} & n_{22} & \dots & n_{2r} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ n_{r1} & n_{r2} & \dots & n_{rr} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} J_1 \\ J_2 \\ \vdots \\ J_r \end{pmatrix} \quad \dots(2)$$

then the new forces X'_i will be given by the following relation :

$$\begin{pmatrix} X'_1 \\ X'_2 \\ \vdots \\ X'_r \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} n_{11} & n_{21} & \dots & n_{r1} \\ n_{12} & n_{22} & \dots & n_{r2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ n_{1r} & n_{2r} & \dots & n_{rr} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} X_1 \\ X_2 \\ \vdots \\ X_r \end{pmatrix} \quad \dots (3)$$

and the n th order coefficient L_n by the expression

$$\begin{aligned} L_n = & L(11..n) (22..n) \dots (rr..n) \\ = & \left(n_{11}^n n_{21}^n \dots n_{r1}^n \right) \left(\frac{\partial^n J_1}{\partial X_1^n} \right)_0 + \left(n_{12}^n n_{22}^n \dots n_{r2}^n \right) \\ & \left(\frac{\partial^n J_2}{\partial X_2^n} \right)_0 + \dots + \left(n_{1r}^n n_{2r}^n \dots n_{rr}^n \right) \left(\frac{\partial^n J_r}{\partial X_r^n} \right)_0 \dots(4) \end{aligned}$$

where $\sum_{i=1}^r n_i = n+1$.

We now examine the following situations :

(a) If higher order symmetry relation can exist when unequal number of fluxes are used in the linear combination, i.e., some elements n_{ik} 's are zero in the transformation matrix N .

(b) If the higher order symmetries could be observed when the processes involved in the linear combination have unequal number and different order of independence.

In dealing with the first situation we find that in the event when an element $n_{ik} = 0$ the k th term in eq. (4) vanishes in all the n th order coefficients in which the number n_i of the integer i in their subscripts is none-zero. In fact $n_{ik} = 0$ implies that the flux J_k has not been included in the linear combination to form the total rate process J'_i . It becomes thus obvious that the exclusion of a flux J_k in the formation of any total rate process makes the k th

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term vanishing only, without in any way affecting the general symmetry relations. This will be true in those situations also where more than one flux are excluded in the transformations resulting in many terms in eq. (4) to vanish. However, if along with the condition $n_{ik}=0$, $n_i=0$ also holds simultaneously, the situation becomes a little different without producing any substantial effect on the general symmetries. In this situation the k th term will not vanish because of the absence of n_{ik} in eq. (4) and all the n th order coefficients in which integer i is absent, will contain k th term also keeping the general symmetry relations intact.

In dealing with the second situation where linear combinations of processes of unequal number and different order of independence are carried out the independence of the total rate process is governed by the highest order of independence of the processes used in such combinations. As a result of this some of the total rate processes will be associated with greater number of higher order coefficient in comparison to the other ones. But this is expected to be so simply because of the inclusion of some fluxes in some of the total processes and their exclusion from others ; a condition under which we have just discussed above that higher order symmetries remain undisturbed. Thus in the present situation higher order symmetries will remain unaffected.

Let us now examine the implication of imposing the above conditions on special symmetry relations which depend on the odd or even character of n_i . Imposition of the condition $n_{ik}=0$ implies that the k th term in L_n may either be zero or non-zero according as $n_i \neq 0$ or $n_i=0$ respectively. It thereby suggests that the value of L_n will depend on the kind of integer i and not on the character of its number n_i . An extension of this situation on account of the presence of more than one zero element in the matrix of transformation may ultimately lead to circumstances in which special symmetry relation

have to depend on the kind of integers present in the subscript of L_n only.

In the subsequent paragraph we first proceed to give an exposition of different facets of the above discussion with a suitable illustration and thereafter discuss some physically meaningful symmetry relations in a few cases of importance and practical interests.

Example : Let us consider three fluxes J_1 of second order independence and J_2 and J_3 each of third order independence. If the new fluxes formed as linear combinations of these fluxes be

$$\begin{aligned} J'_1 &= J_1 + J_2 + J_3 \\ J'_2 &= J_1 + 2J_2 + 0J_3 \\ \text{and } J'_3 &= J_1 + 0J_2 + 2J_3 \end{aligned} \quad \dots \quad (a)$$

then transformation matrix N will be represented as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{1} & 1 & \bar{1} \\ 1 & 2 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \quad \dots \quad (b)$$

N

Since N is symmetric the original conjugate forces X_1, X_2 and X_3 corresponding to fluxes J_1, J_2 and J_3 in view of eq (3) will be given by

$$\begin{aligned} X_1 &= X'_1 + X'_2 + X'_3 \\ X_2 &= X'_1 + 2X'_2 + 0X'_3 \\ X_3 &= X'_1 + 0X'_2 + 2X'_3 \end{aligned} \quad \dots \quad (c)$$

where X'_1, X'_2 and X'_3 are new conjugate forces.

Now on substitution of J_1, J_2 and J_3 by the values of X_1, X_2 and X_3 in terms of new forces in (a) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} J'_1 &= \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial X_1} \right)_o + \left(\frac{\partial J_2}{\partial X_2} \right)_o + \left(\frac{\partial J_3}{\partial X_3} \right)_o \right\} X'_1 + \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial X_1} \right)_o + 2 \left(\frac{\partial J_2}{\partial X_2} \right)_o \right\} X'_2 + \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial X_1} \right)_o + 2 \left(\frac{\partial J_3}{\partial X_3} \right)_o \right\} X'_3 \\ &+ \frac{1}{2!} \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o + \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_o + \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_3}{\partial X_3^2} \right)_o \right\} X'^2_1 + \frac{1}{2!} \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o + 4 \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_o \right\} X'^2_2 + \frac{1}{2!} \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o + 4 \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_3}{\partial X_3^2} \right)_o \right\} X'^2_3 \\ &+ \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o + 2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_o \right\} X'_1 X'_2 + \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o + 2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_3}{\partial X_3^2} \right)_o \right\} X'_1 X'_3 + \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o \right\} X'_2 X'_3 \\ &+ \frac{1}{3!} \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_2}{\partial X_2^3} \right)_o + \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_3}{\partial X_3^3} \right)_o \right\} X'^3_2 + \frac{1}{3!} \left\{ 8 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_2}{\partial X_2^3} \right)_o \right\} X'^3_3 + \frac{1}{3!} \left\{ 8 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_3}{\partial X_3^3} \right)_o \right\} X'^3_3 + \frac{1}{2!} \left\{ 2 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_2}{\partial X_2^3} \right)_o \right\} X'^2_1 X'_2 \\ &+ \frac{1}{2!} \left\{ 4 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_2}{\partial X_2^3} \right)_o \right\} X'_1 X'^2_2 + \frac{1}{2!} \left\{ 2 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_3}{\partial X_3^3} \right)_o \right\} X'^2_1 X'_3 + \frac{1}{2!} \left\{ 4 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_3}{\partial X_3^3} \right)_o \right\} X'_1 X'^2_3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 J'_2 = & \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial X_1} \right)_o + 2 \left(\frac{\partial J_2}{\partial X_2} \right)_o \right\} X'_1 + \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial X_1} \right)_o + 4 \left(\frac{\partial J_2}{\partial X_2} \right)_o \right\} X'_2 + \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial X_1} \right)_o \right\} X'_3 + \frac{1}{2!} \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o + 2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_o \right\} X'^2_1 \\
 & + \frac{1}{2!} \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o + 8 \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_o \right\} X'^2_2 + \frac{1}{2!} \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o \right\} X'^2_3 + \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o + 4 \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_o \right\} X'_1 X'_2 + \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o \right\} X'_1 X'_3 \\
 & + \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o \right\} X'_2 X'_3 + \frac{1}{3!} \left\{ 2 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_2}{\partial X_2^3} \right)_o \right\} X'^3_1 + \frac{1}{3!} \left\{ 16 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_2}{\partial X_2^3} \right)_o \right\} X'^3_2 + \frac{1}{2!} \left\{ 4 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_2}{\partial X_2^3} \right)_o \right\} X'^2_1 X'_2 \\
 & + \frac{1}{2!} \left\{ 8 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_2}{\partial X_2^3} \right)_o \right\} X'_1 X'^2_2.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 J'_3 = & \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial X_1} \right)_o + 2 \left(\frac{\partial J_2}{\partial X_2} \right)_o \right\} X'_1 + \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial X_1} \right)_o \right\} X'_2 + \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial X_1} \right)_o + 4 \left(\frac{\partial J_2}{\partial X_2} \right)_o \right\} X'_3 \\
 & + \frac{1}{2!} \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o + 2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_o \right\} X'^2_1 + \frac{1}{2!} \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o \right\} X'^2_2 + \frac{1}{2!} \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o + 8 \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_o \right\} X'^2_3 + \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o \right\} X'_1 X'_2 \\
 & + \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o + 4 \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_o \right\} X'_1 X'_3 + \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o \right\} X'_2 X'_3 + \frac{1}{3!} \left\{ 2 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_2}{\partial X_2^3} \right)_o \right\} X'^3_1 + \frac{1}{3!} \left\{ 16 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_2}{\partial X_2^3} \right)_o \right\} X'^3_2 \\
 & + \frac{1}{2!} \left\{ 4 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_2}{\partial X_2^3} \right)_o \right\} X'^2_1 X'_3 + \frac{1}{2!} \left\{ 8 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_2}{\partial X_2^3} \right)_o \right\} X'_1 X'^2_2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus we obtain the following symmetry relations (abbreviations G. S. and S. S. indicate general symmetry and special symmetry respectively) :

	term/terms of	being absent	(G. S.)
$L_{12} = L_{21} = \left(\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial X_1} \right)_o + 2 \left(\frac{\partial J_2}{\partial X_2} \right)_o$	$\left(\frac{\partial J_3}{\partial X_3} \right)_o$		
$L_{13} = L_{31} = \left(\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial X_1} \right)_o + 2 \left(\frac{\partial J_3}{\partial X_3} \right)_o$	" "	$\left(\frac{\partial J_2}{\partial X_2} \right)_o$	"
$L_{23} = L_{32} = \left(\frac{\partial J_1}{\partial X_1} \right)_o$	" "	$\left(\frac{\partial J_2}{\partial X_2} \right)_o, \left(\frac{\partial J_3}{\partial X_3} \right)_o$	"
$L_{112} = L_{211} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o + 2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_o$	" "	$\left(\frac{\partial^2 J_3}{\partial X_3^2} \right)_o$	"
$L_{122} = L_{212} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o + 4 \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_o$	" "	$\left(\frac{\partial^2 J_3}{\partial X_3^2} \right)_o$	"
$L_{113} = L_{311} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o + 2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_3}{\partial X_3^2} \right)_o$	" "	$\left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_o$	"
$L_{123} = L_{213} = L_{312} = L_{233} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o$	" "	$\left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_o, \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_3}{\partial X_3^2} \right)_o$	(S. S.)
$L_{323} = L_{223} = L_{322} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o$	" "	" "	"
$L_{133} = L_{313} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_1}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_o + 4 \left(\frac{\partial^2 J_3}{\partial X_3^2} \right)_o$	" "	$\left(\frac{\partial^2 J_2}{\partial X_2^2} \right)_o$	(G. S.)

	term/terms of	being absent	(G. S.)
$L_{1112} = L_{2111} = 2 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_2}{\partial X_2^3} \right)_0$	" "	$\left(\frac{\partial^3 J_1}{\partial X_1^3} \right)_0, \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_3}{\partial X_3^3} \right)_0$	" "
$L_{1122} = L_{2112} = 4 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_2}{\partial X_2^3} \right)_0$	" "	$\left(\frac{\partial^3 J_1}{\partial X_1^3} \right)_0, \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_3}{\partial X_3^3} \right)_0$	" "
$L_{1222} = L_{2122} = 8 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_2}{\partial X_2^3} \right)_0$	" "	$\left(\frac{\partial^3 J_1}{\partial X_1^3} \right)_0, \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_3}{\partial X_3^3} \right)_0$	" "
$L_{1113} = L_{3111} = 2 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_3}{\partial X_3^3} \right)_0$	" "	$\left(\frac{\partial^3 J_1}{\partial X_1^3} \right)_0, \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_2}{\partial X_2^3} \right)_0$	" "
$L_{1133} = L_{3113} = 4 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_3}{\partial X_3^3} \right)_0$	" "	$\left(\frac{\partial^3 J_1}{\partial X_1^3} \right)_0, \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_2}{\partial X_2^3} \right)_0$	" "
$L_{1333} = L_{3133} = 8 \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_3}{\partial X_3^3} \right)_0$	" "	$\left(\frac{\partial^3 J_1}{\partial X_1^3} \right)_0, \left(\frac{\partial^3 J_2}{\partial X_2^3} \right)_0$	" "
$L_{1223} = L_{2123} = L_{3123} = L_{1123} = L_{3113} = 0$		Non existent	(S. S.)
$L_{3112} = L_{1233} = L_{2133} = L_{3123} = L_{2333} = 0$		"	"
$L_{3233} = L_{2233} = L_{3223} = L_{3223} = L_{3222} = 0$		"	"

Since $n_{22} = 0$ and $n_{32} = 0$ in the above transformation matrix N in (b) the coefficients having integer 2 or 3 do not contain the terms with derivatives of J_3 or J_2 respectively and the coefficients having both the integers are free from the terms containing derivatives of J_2 and J_3 . Whereas the coefficients free from integer 2 or 3 or both contain terms with derivatives of J_3 or J_2 or both as the case may be. Thus second order coefficients containing integers 2 and 3 show special symmetry relations.

Further as the third order coefficients do not have terms of derivatives of J_1 which has only second order independence, third order coefficients containing both integer 2 and 3 are non-existent.

Thus the results obtained in the above example are in agreement with the theoretical considerations.

Realisation of Symmetries in some 'Transport Processes :

The most important aspect of the study of higher order symmetries is to find out appropriate situation where they may be found to hold in transport processes. It has been shown⁵ by Rastogi et al that such symmetries have physical meaning in some chemical reactions under suitable conditions. However, their presence in other transport processes is still not well recognised and needs proper considerations. In the following lines we would like to point out a few situations where such symmetries in transport processes appear to be physically meaningful.

Electro-kinetics :

In electro-kinetics the electro-osmotic flow J_E and solve dynamic flow J_S together constitute the matter flow J . But from classical theory it is known that electro-osmotic flow J_E is related¹³ to current flow I as

$$J_E/I = \frac{\xi D}{4\pi\eta K} = K_1 \text{ or } J_E = K_1 I \quad \dots(i)$$

Hence the total matter flow J and current I may be represented by the following linear combinations

$$J = J_S + J_E = J_S + K_1 I \quad \dots(ii)$$

$$I = 0 J_S + I \quad \dots(iii)$$

If ΔP and $\Delta\varphi$ be the applied pressure and electrical potential respectively then the net electrical potential in the system will be¹⁴ $\Delta\varphi + K_1 \Delta P$, where $K_1 \Delta P$ is the developed streaming potential. Thus conjugate forces corresponding to fluxes J_S and I are ΔP and $\Delta\varphi + K_1 \Delta P$ respectively. The new forces X'_1 and X'_2 corresponding to the total fluxes J and I will, therefore, be given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta P \\ \Delta\varphi + K_1 \Delta P \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ K_1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X'_1 \\ X'_2 \end{bmatrix} \dots(iv)$$

that is $X'_1 = \Delta P$ and $K_1 X'_1 + X'_2 = \Delta\varphi + K_1 \Delta P$

$$\text{or } X'_2 = \Delta\varphi \quad \dots(v)$$

Since J_s and I are non-linear in nature they may be written as :

$$J_s = L_{11}\Delta P + \frac{1}{2!}L_{111}(\Delta P)^2 + \frac{1}{3!}L_{1111}(\Delta P)^3 + \dots \text{ (vi)}$$

$$I = L_{22}(\Delta\varphi + K_1\Delta P) + \frac{1}{2!}L_{222}(\Delta\varphi + K_1\Delta P)^2 + \frac{1}{3!}L_{2222}(\Delta\varphi + K_1\Delta P)^3 + \dots \text{ (vii)}$$

Using the expressions for J_s and I in eqs. (ii) and (iii) we obtain

$$J = (L_{11} + K_1^2 L_{22}) (\Delta P) + K_1 L_{22} (\Delta\varphi) + \frac{1}{2!} (L_{111} + K_1^2 L_{222}) (\Delta P)^2 + K_1^2 L_{222} (\Delta P) (\Delta\varphi) + \frac{1}{2!} K_1 L_{222} (\Delta\varphi)^2 + \dots \text{ (viii)}$$

$$I = K_1 L_{22} (\Delta P) + L_{22} (\Delta\varphi) + \frac{1}{2!} K_1^2 L_{222} (\Delta P)^2 + K_1 L_{222} (\Delta P) (\Delta\varphi) + \frac{1}{2!} L_{222} (\Delta\varphi)^2 + \dots \text{ (ix)}$$

If J and I represent fluxes 1 and 2 respectively and the primed L 's represent their coefficients then we obtain the following symmetries from eqs. (viii) and (ix)

$$\begin{aligned} L'_{12} &= L'_{21} = K_1 \cdot L_{22} \\ L'_{112} &= L'_{211} = K_1^2 \cdot L_{222} \\ L'_{122} &= L'_{212} = K_1 \cdot L_{222} \dots \end{aligned}$$

Thermo-osmosis :

In case of thermo-osmosis the driving force for the elementary flux of matter J_1 is the applied pressure ΔP plus the developed thermo-osmotic pressure $K_1\Delta T$ on account of the temperature difference ΔT in the system and the force corresponding to heat flow J_2 by conduction is ΔT . Since transfer of heat is also caused by the flow of matter the total heat flow H contains this part in addition to J_2 . Under these circumstances the total matter flow J and heat flow H may be represented by the following linear combinations of the elementary fluxes J_1 and J_2 :

$$J = J_1 + 0 J_2 \dots \text{ (i)}$$

$$H = J_1 K_1 + J_2 \dots \text{ (ii)}$$

where $K_1 = S$ (specific heat of the permeant) $\times \Delta T$.

Thus from thermodynamic consideration the conjugate forces X'_1 and X'_2 corresponding to total fluxes J and H will be given by the relation :

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta P + K_1 \Delta T \\ \Delta T \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & K_1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X'_1 \\ X'_2 \end{bmatrix} \text{ (iii)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{that is } \Delta P + K_1 \Delta T &= X'_1 + K_1 X'_2 \text{ and } \Delta T = X'_2 \\ \text{or } X'_1 &= \Delta P \text{ and } X'_2 = \Delta T \end{aligned} \text{ (iv)}$$

In view of Poissuille's equation¹⁴ the matter flow J_1 may be written as :

$$J_1 = L_{11}(\Delta P + K_1 \Delta T) + \frac{1}{2!}L_{111}(\Delta P + K_1 \Delta T)^2 + \dots \text{ (v)}$$

and further J_2 by Fourier's law of heat conduction as :

$$J_2 = L_{22}(\Delta T) \dots \text{ (vi)}$$

Using these expressions for J_1 and J_2 in eqs. (i) and (ii) we obtain J and H as :

$$\begin{aligned} J &= L_{11}(\Delta P) + K_1 L_{11}(\Delta T) + \frac{1}{2!}L_{111}(\Delta P)^2 + K_1 L_{111}(\Delta P)(\Delta T) + \frac{1}{2!}K_1^2 L_{111}(\Delta T)^2 + \dots \text{ (vii)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } H &= K_1 L_{11}(\Delta P) + (K_1^2 L_{11} + L_{22})(\Delta T) + \frac{1}{2!}K_1 L_{111}(\Delta P)^2 + K_1^2 L_{111}(\Delta P)(\Delta T) + \frac{1}{2!}K_1^2 L_{111}(\Delta T)^2 + \dots \text{ (viii)} \end{aligned}$$

From eqs. (vii) and (viii), therefore, in line with electro-kinetics we obtain the following symmetries :

$$\begin{aligned} L'_{12} &= L'_{21} = K_1 L_{11} ; L'_{112} = L'_{211} = K_1 L_{111} ; \\ L'_{122} &= L'_{212} = K_1^2 L_{111} \dots \end{aligned}$$

Salt filtration (Electrolyte) :

In case of a Z_2, Z_3 valent electrolytic solution the elementary fluxes which occur in the system are those of molecules of solvent and two types of ionic species. If J_1, J_2 and J_3 respectively denote these fluxes then chemical potential difference of solvent $\Delta\mu_1$ and electro-chemical potential differences $\Delta\hat{\mu}_2$ and $\Delta\hat{\mu}_3$ act as driving forces for the respective species. From thermodynamic consideration¹⁵⁻¹⁹ it is known²⁰ that $\Delta\mu_1 = V_1(\Delta P - \Delta\pi)$, $\Delta\pi$ being the osmotic pressure of the solution and the chemical potential of the salt $\Delta\mu_s$ is related to the electro-chemical potentials of the ionic species by the relation^{21,22}

$$\Delta\mu_s = \nu_2 \Delta\hat{\mu}_2 + \nu_3 \Delta\hat{\mu}_3 \dots \text{ (i)}$$

where ν_2 and ν_3 are the number of ions which are obtained by the dissociation of one molecule of salt. For electroneutrality

$$\nu_2 Z_2 + \nu_3 Z_3 = 0 \dots \text{ (ii)}$$

Further the e.m.f. $\Delta\varphi$ acting in the system with respect to the electrodes reversible to the ion 2 (say) may be described by

$$\Delta\varphi = \frac{\Delta\hat{\mu}_2}{Z_2 F} \dots \text{ (iii)}$$

Thus the forces may be conveniently written as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\mu_1 &= V_1(\Delta P - \Delta\pi) \\ \Delta\hat{\mu}_2 &= Z_2 F \Delta\varphi \quad \dots \quad (iv) \\ \Delta\hat{\mu}_3 &= \frac{\Delta\mu_s}{\gamma_s} - \frac{\gamma_2 Z_2 F \Delta\varphi}{\gamma_s} = \frac{\Delta\mu_s}{\gamma_s} + Z_3 F \Delta\varphi \end{aligned}$$

Now volume flow J_V electrical current I and salt flow J_s may be obtained as linear combinations of the elementary fluxes J_1 , J_2 and J_3 as given under :

$$\begin{aligned} J_V &= J_1 V_1 + J_s V_s = J_1 V_1 + \frac{J_s V_s}{\gamma_s} \\ I &= Z_2 F J_2 + Z_3 F J_3 \\ J_s &= \frac{J_s}{\gamma_s} \end{aligned}$$

i.e.,
$$\begin{pmatrix} J_V \\ I \\ J_s \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} V_1 & 0 & \frac{V_s}{\gamma_s} \\ 0 & Z_2 F & Z_3 F \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{\gamma_s} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} J_1 \\ J_2 \\ J_3 \end{pmatrix} \dots (v)$$

where V 's stand for molar volumes of the different species.

The conjugate forces X'_1 , X'_2 and X'_3 corresponding to these new fluxes, therefore, may be obtained from the relation

$$\begin{pmatrix} V_1(\Delta P - \Delta\pi) \\ Z_2 F \Delta\varphi \\ \frac{\Delta\mu_s}{\gamma_s} + Z_3 F \Delta\varphi \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} V_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & Z_2 F & 0 \\ \frac{V_s}{\gamma_s} & Z_3 F & \frac{1}{\gamma_s} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} X'_1 \\ X'_2 \\ X'_3 \end{pmatrix} \dots (vi)$$

Thus $V_1 X'_1 = V_1(\Delta P - \Delta\pi)$ or $X'_1 = (\Delta P - \Delta\pi)$
 $Z_2 F X'_2 = Z_2 F \Delta\varphi$ or $X'_2 = \Delta\varphi \quad \dots (vii)$

$$\frac{V_s X'_3}{\gamma_s} + Z_3 F X'_2 + \frac{X'_3}{\gamma_s} = \frac{\Delta\mu_s}{\gamma_s} + Z_3 F \Delta\varphi$$

or $X'_3 = (C_s V_s + 1) \frac{\Delta\pi}{C_s} \approx \frac{\Delta\pi}{C_s}$

[$\because C_s V_s$ is small for dilute solution and²⁰

$$\Delta\mu_s = \left(V_s \cdot \Delta P + \frac{\Delta\pi}{C_s} \right).$$

Since the fluxes through membrane capillaries are governed by Poiseuille's equation we may represent J_1 , J_2 and J_3 in the power series of forces as :

$$J_1 = L_{11} V_1 (\Delta P - \Delta\pi) + \frac{1}{2!} L_{111} V_1^2 (\Delta P - \Delta\pi)^2 + \dots$$

$$J_2 = L_{22} (Z_2 F \Delta\varphi) + \frac{1}{2!} L_{222} (Z_2 F \Delta\varphi)^2 + \dots$$

$$\begin{aligned} J_3 &= L_{33} \left(\frac{\Delta\mu_s}{\gamma_s} + Z_3 F \Delta\varphi \right) \\ &+ \frac{1}{2!} L_{333} \left(\frac{\Delta\mu_s}{\gamma_s} + Z_3 F \Delta\varphi \right)^2 + \dots \quad \dots (viii) \end{aligned}$$

Inserting these expressions for J_1 , J_2 and J_3 in eq. (iv) along with the values of the forces in terms of the new forces from eq. (vii) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} J_V &= \left(V_1^2 L_{11} + \frac{V_s^2}{\gamma_s^2} L_{33} \right) (\Delta P - \Delta\pi) \\ &+ \frac{V_s Z_3 F}{\gamma_s} L_{33} (\Delta\varphi) + \frac{V_s}{\gamma_s^2} L_{33} \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_s} \right) \\ &+ \frac{1}{2!} \left(V_1^2 L_{111} + \frac{V_s^2}{\gamma_s^2} L_{333} \right) (\Delta P - \Delta\pi)^2 \\ &+ \frac{1}{2!} \frac{V_s Z_3^2 F^2}{\gamma_s} L_{333} (\Delta\varphi)^2 \\ &+ \frac{1}{2!} \frac{V_s}{\gamma_s^2} L_{333} \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_s} \right)^2 + \frac{V_s^2 Z_3 F}{\gamma_s^2} L_{333} (\Delta P - \Delta\pi) (\Delta\varphi) \\ &+ \frac{V_s^2}{\gamma_s^2} L_{333} (\Delta P - \Delta\pi) \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_s} \right) \\ &+ \frac{V_s Z_3 F}{\gamma_s^2} L_{333} (\Delta\varphi) \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_s} \right) + \dots \quad \dots (ix) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} I &= \frac{Z_2 F V_s}{\gamma_s} L_{33} (\Delta P - \Delta\pi) \\ &+ (Z_2^2 F^2 L_{22} + Z_3^2 F^2 L_{33}) (\Delta\varphi) + \frac{Z_3 F}{\gamma_s} L_{33} \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_s} \right) \\ &+ \frac{1}{2!} \frac{Z_2 F V_s^2}{\gamma_s^2} L_{333} (\Delta P - \Delta\pi)^2 \\ &+ \frac{1}{2!} (Z_2^2 F^2 L_{222} + Z_3^2 F^2 L_{333}) (\Delta\varphi)^2 \\ &+ \frac{1}{2!} \frac{Z_3 F}{\gamma_s^2} L_{333} \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_s} \right)^2 + \frac{Z_3^2 F^2 V_s}{\gamma_s} L_{333} (\Delta P - \Delta\pi) (\Delta\varphi) \\ &+ \frac{Z_3 F V_s}{\gamma_s^2} L_{333} (\Delta P - \Delta\pi) \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_s} \right) \\ &+ \frac{Z_3^2 F^2 V_s}{\gamma_s} L_{333} (\Delta\varphi) \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_s} \right) + \dots \quad \dots (x) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} J_s &= \frac{V_s}{\gamma_s^2} L_{33} (\Delta P - \Delta\pi) + \frac{Z_3 F}{\gamma_s} L_{33} (\Delta\varphi) \\ &+ \frac{1}{\gamma_s^2} L_{33} \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_s} \right) + \frac{1}{2!} \frac{V_s}{\gamma_s^2} L_{333} (\Delta P - \Delta\pi)^2 \\ &+ \frac{1}{2!} \frac{Z_3^2 F^2}{\gamma_s} L_{333} (\Delta\varphi)^2 + \frac{1}{2!} \frac{1}{\gamma_s} L_{333} \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_s} \right)^2 \\ &+ \frac{V_s Z_3 F}{\gamma_s^2} L_{333} (\Delta P - \Delta\pi) (\Delta\varphi) \\ &+ \frac{V_s}{\gamma_s^2} L_{333} (\Delta P - \Delta\pi) \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_s} \right) \\ &+ \frac{Z_3 F}{\gamma_s^2} L_{333} (\Delta\varphi) \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_s} \right) + \dots \quad \dots (xi) \end{aligned}$$

If integers 1, 2 and 3 denote J_V , I and J_S respectively and primed L's stand for their coefficients then from eqs. (ix)-(xi) we obtain the following symmetries:

$$L'_{12} = L'_{21} = \frac{(V_S Z_3 F L_{33})}{\gamma_3}; L'_{13} = L'_{31} = \frac{(V_S L_{33})}{\gamma_3^2}$$

$$L'_{23} = L'_{32} = \frac{(Z_3 F L_{33})}{\gamma_3}$$

$$L'_{112} = L'_{211} = \frac{(V_S^2 Z_3 F L_{33})}{\gamma_3^2};$$

$$L'_{122} = L'_{212} = \frac{(V_S Z_3^2 F^2 L_{33})}{\gamma_3}$$

$$L'_{113} = L'_{311} = \frac{(V_S^2 L_{33})}{\gamma_3^2}; L'_{133} = L'_{313} = \frac{(V_S L_{33})}{\gamma_3^2}$$

$$L'_{132} = L'_{213} = L'_{312} = \frac{(Z_3 F V_S L_{33})}{\gamma_3^2}; \dots$$

Salt filtration (Non-electrolyte) :

In case of a non-electrolytic solution under the gradient of pressure and chemical potential it is invariably found that salt filtration can occur through membrane of wide pore size capillaries and, therefore, the process is different from mechanical sieving effect.

From thermodynamic consideration it is known that driving forces for the fluxes of solvent J_W and solute J_S are their chemical potentials :

$$\Delta\mu_W = V_W(\Delta P - \Delta\pi), \quad \Delta\mu_S = \left(V_S \Delta P + \frac{\Delta\pi}{C_S} \right) \dots (i)$$

respectively. The different quantities involved in eq. (i) have their usual significance.

Since the flow of matter in a capillary tube is governed by Poiseuille's equation the fluxes $J_1 = J_W V_W$ and $J_2 = J_S V_S$ may be represented as :

$$J_1 = L_{11}(\Delta P - \Delta\pi) + \frac{1}{2!} L_{111}(\Delta P - \Delta\pi)^2 + \frac{1}{3!} L_{1111}(\Delta P - \Delta\pi)^3 + \dots$$

$$J_2 = L_{22} \left(\Delta P + \frac{\Delta\pi}{C_S V_S} \right) + \frac{1}{2!} L_{222} \left(\Delta P + \frac{\Delta\pi}{C_S V_S} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{3!} L_{2222} \left(\Delta P + \frac{\Delta\pi}{C_S V_S} \right)^3 + \dots \dots (ii)$$

Now we obtain the following fluxes as linear combination of J_1 and J_2

$$J'_1 = J_1 + J_2 \quad \begin{bmatrix} J'_1 \\ J'_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} J_1 \\ J_2 \end{bmatrix} \dots (iii)$$

where J'_1 is total volume flow and J'_2 is volume of salt flow.

The corresponding conjugate forces X'_1 and X'_2 of these new fluxes will, therefore, be given by the relation

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta P - \Delta\pi \\ \Delta P + \frac{\Delta\pi}{C_S V_S} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X'_1 \\ X'_2 \end{bmatrix} \dots (iv)$$

i.e., $X'_1 = \Delta P - \Delta\pi,$

and $X'_2 = (C_S V_S + 1) \frac{\Delta\pi}{C_S V_S} = \frac{\Delta\pi}{C_S V_S} \dots (v)$

Inserting the expressions for J_1 and J_2 from eq. (ii) into eq. (iii) along with the values of forces in terms of new forces from eq. (v) we obtain

$$J'_1 = (L_{11} + L_{22})(\Delta P - \Delta\pi) + L_{22} \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_S V_S} \right) + \frac{1}{2!} (L_{111} + L_{222})(\Delta P - \Delta\pi)^2 + L_{222}(\Delta P - \Delta\pi) \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_S V_S} \right) + \frac{1}{2!} L_{222} \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_S V_S} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{3!} (L_{1111} + L_{2222})(\Delta P - \Delta\pi)^3 + \frac{1}{2!} L_{2222}(\Delta P - \Delta\pi)^2 \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_S V_S} \right) + \frac{1}{2!} L_{2222}(\Delta P - \Delta\pi) \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_S V_S} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{3!} L_{2222} \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_S V_S} \right)^3 + \dots \dots (vi)$$

$$J'_2 = L_{22}(\Delta P - \Delta\pi) + L_{22} \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_S V_S} \right) + \frac{1}{2!} L_{222}(\Delta P - \Delta\pi)^2 + L_{222}(\Delta P - \Delta\pi) \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_S V_S} \right) + \frac{1}{2!} L_{222} \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_S V_S} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{3!} L_{2222}(\Delta P - \Delta\pi)^3 + \frac{1}{2!} L_{2222}(\Delta P - \Delta\pi) \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_S V_S} \right) + \frac{1}{2!} L_{2222}(\Delta P - \Delta\pi) \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_S V_S} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{3!} L_{2222} \left(\frac{\Delta\pi}{C_S V_S} \right)^3 + \dots \dots (vii)$$

If primed L's denote the coefficients of J'_1 and J'_2 we obtain the following symmetries from eqs. (vi) and (vii) :

$$L'_{12} = L'_{21} = (L_{22}) = L'_{22}$$

$$L'_{112} = L'_{211} = (L_{222}) = L'_{122} = L'_{212} = L'_{222}$$

$$L'_{1112} = L'_{2111} = (L_{2222}) = L'_{1122} = L'_{2112} = L'_{2222} = L'_{1222} = L'_{2122} = L'_{2222} \dots$$

Since $n_{21} = 0$ in the transformation matrix in eq. (iv) coefficients $L_{11}, L_{111}, L_{1111} \dots$ contain two

terms and the special symmetries are independent of the characters of integers 1 and 2. Thus we find that all the coefficients containing integers 1 and 2 or 2 only are equal.

From what has been discussed above it would be clear that the higher order symmetries can be visualised with full physical significance in a number of transport processes. The crux of the problem appears to be the identification of the fluxes and forces in the process of linear combinations of the original fluxes and forces in a correct perspective. Once this has been achieved the higher order symmetries appear to follow naturally like a logical consequence.

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